

Supplementary material S2

Sailer, Utley at al.: Lanes, Clusters, Lines of Sight

Pseudocode for the queuing simulations

The pseudocode below outlines how the queuing simulation operates for a single experimental combination of ostensive process and appointment schedule. Key variables are given in bold using a convention that **variable_{*i*}** represents a vector with elements indexed *i* and **variable_{*j*_{*k*}}** represents a two-dimensional array with elements indexed (*j*,*k*). The R code is provided.

1. Assign values to:

NumRuns the number of simulation runs per experiment, indexed *r*

Seed_{*r*} the random number seed to be used for run *r*

NumPats the number of patients given appointments, indexed *p*

NumActivities the number of clinical tests patients undergo, indexed *a*

DNAProb the probability that a patient does not attend.

2. For the ostensive process considered, assign values to

NumQueues – the number of queues for the ostensive process, indexed *q*

a_{*q*} - the activity associated with each queue *q*

NumServers_{*q*} – the number of servers (pieces of equipment) serving queue *q*

NextQueue_{*q*_{*s*}} – the next queue joined by those served by server *s* at queue *q*

TransitTime_{*q*_{*s*}} – the time taken to join next queue from server *s* at queue *q*

3. For the appointment schedule considered

Form a set of patients \mathbb{P} with patients indexed *p* = 1 to **NumPats**.

Assign an appointment time to each patient as per the appointment schedule.

For all patients $p \in \mathbb{P}$, initialise **NQ_{*p*}**, to 1 (the first queue they would visit under this ostensive process).

4. Initialise each run *r*:

Set the random number seed to **Seed_{*r*}**

For each patient $p \in \mathbb{P}$ randomly sample a set of activity times from a collection of observed patient journeys.

For each patient $p \in \mathbb{P}$ determine attendance as a Bernoulli trial with probability of success (1-DNAProb).

Create subset $\mathbb{A} \subseteq \mathbb{P}$ of patients that attend the clinic.

For each patient $p \in \mathbb{A}$ sample a $\text{ClinicArrivalTime}_p$ from their appointment time.

Set variable $\text{NextQueueArrivalTime}_p$ to $\text{ClinicArrivalTime}_p$ for that patient.

5. For each queue from $q = 1$ to NumQueues

Form set $\mathbb{A}_q \subseteq \mathbb{A}$ of patients p with $\mathbf{NQ}_p = q$.

Form vectors of $\text{NextQueueArrivalTime}_p$, activity times, and patient indices p from patients $p \in \mathbb{A}_q$, with elements ordered by increasing values of $\text{NextQueueArrivalTime}_p$.

Use $\text{queue_step}()$ function from QComputer package to return

DepartureTime_p for each patient $p \in \mathbb{A}_q$

s the identifier for the server used by each patient $p \in \mathbb{A}_q$

Use the $\text{average_queue}()$ function from QComputer to return

The average number of people in queue q for this run under this ostensive process and this appointment schedule. Store values.

Set $\mathbf{NextQueueArrivalTime}_p = \mathbf{DepartureTime}_p + \mathbf{TransitTime}_{q_s}$ for each patient $p \in \mathbb{A}_q$

Set $\mathbf{NQ}_p = \mathbf{NextQueue}_{q_s}$ for each patient $p \in \mathbb{A}_q$

6. Take clinic duration for run r under this ostensive process and this appointment schedule as the largest value of $\text{NextQueueArrivalTime}_p$ among $p \in \mathbb{A}$

7. Repeat steps 4 to 6 for each run up to NumRuns

8. Calculate average over runs of average queue size for each queue, and average over runs of clinic duration from stored values.